

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOEMULSION FROM CINNAMON BARK ESSENTIAL OIL (*CINNAMOMUM BURMANII*)

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ABSTRACT

Nanoemulsions have advantages over similar emulsions that have larger sizes, including being more reactive. Cinnamon bark (*Cinnamomum burmanii*) essential oil nanoemulsions were formulated using the spontaneous emulsification method with Tween 80 surfactant and PEG 400 cosurfactant. Cinnamon bark essential oil nanoemulsions were characterized using PSA, FTIR, and TEM. The results showed that the nanoemulsion had a particle size of 9.76–12.92 nm with a PDI value <0.3 and a zeta potential of –9.96 to –15.33 mV. FTIR analysis showed that the main functional groups of essential oils from steam distillation compared to after being made into nanoemulsions remained stable. TEM results showed spherical particles with a homogeneous distribution. These results prove that nanoemulsion formulation can increase the effectiveness and stability of cinnamon bark essential oil.

KEYWORDS: *Cinnamomum burmanii*, nanoemulsion, essential oil.

INTRODUCTION

Nanoemulsions are submicron colloidal particle systems that function as carriers for drug molecules with a size of approximately 5–200 nm.^[1] Nanoemulsions can increase stability, expand surface area, and enhance drug delivery efficiency and bioavailability.^[2] Nanoemulsions are typically prepared by mixing an oil phase, surfactant, cosurfactant, and a

water phase.^[3] They have the ability to increase the solubility of natural ingredients, particularly by enhancing the elimination, absorption, permeability, and bioavailability of active ingredients.^[2]

Virgin coconut oil (VCO) is a frequently used method for nanoemulsion production due to its medium-chain triglyceride (MCT) content, which can produce nanoemulsions with better stability and clarity than oils containing long-chain triglycerides (LCT).^[4] VCO has high biocompatibility and safety, as well as anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties that support the therapeutic potential of the formulated nanoemulsions.^[5]

To ensure the stability and effectiveness of essential oils in nanoemulsion delivery systems, the various components used in nanoemulsion formulations are crucial. One of the main components involved in nanoemulsion formation is surfactants, which function to reduce the surface tension at the interface between the oil and water phases through an absorption process at the boundary separating the two liquids.^[6]

Nonionic surfactants, such as Tween 80, are frequently used in nanoemulsion preparation due to their low toxicity and ability to dissolve active ingredients in water, thereby increasing emulsion stability and efficiency.^[7] Cosurfactants, such as Polyethylene Glycol 400 (PEG 400), also play a crucial role in reducing interfacial tension, increasing the flexibility of the surfactant layer, and preventing droplet coalescence, thus maintaining the clarity and distribution of nano-sized droplets.^[8]

In their study, Kristiani *et al.* (2019) formulated a nanoemulsion with basil essential oil using varying concentrations of the surfactant Tween 80 and the cosurfactant PEG 400, resulting in higher antibacterial activity compared to the positive control. This study demonstrated the potential of essential oils in nanoemulsion form as antibacterial agents.^[9]

Purwanjani *et al.* (2021) developed a nanoemulsion of cinnamon (*Cinnamomum burmanii*) extract and evaluated its physical characteristics. The results showed that the resulting nanoemulsions were essential oil-in-water emulsions with different particle sizes for each formula: 24.2 nm for F1, 181.6 nm for F2, and 362.9 nm for F3. Although F1 and F2 met the criteria for nanoemulsions, F3 did not qualify as a nanoemulsion.^[10]

Based on this background, this study aimed to develop nanoemulsions with varying phases of cinnamon bark essential oil and VCO. The resulting nanoemulsion was then tested for its

physico-chemical characteristics using a Particle Size Analyzer (PSA) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Materials and Equipment

The materials used are cinnamon bark (*Cinnamomum burmanii*) obtained from gardens in Belok Village, Petang District, Badung Regency, Bali Province, KBr, n-heksana, VCO, Tween 80, PEG 400, and aquas.

The tools used in this study are a set of distillation tools, measuring cups, beaker glasses, drip pipettes, volume pipettes, vortexes, tissues, scissors, vial bottles, petri dishes, label paper, funnels, spatulas, Erlenmeyer, micro tubes, copper grid, auto carbon coater, Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Particle Size Analyzer (PSA), Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS), and the Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrophotometer.

METHOD

Preparation of test materials

A 1 kg sample of cinnamon bark was prepared, thoroughly cleaned, and then cut into small pieces. Afterward, the sample was weighed, yielding 500 g for steam distillation. A 5 g sample of cinnamon bark was ground for analysis to determine its water content.

Determination of the moisture content of cinnamon bark

The moisture content of cinnamon bark powder was determined using an oven heating method. An empty crucible was first dried in an oven for 60 minutes, then cooled in a desiccator and weighed using an analytical balance. Afterward, 1–3 g of cinnamon bark powder was placed in the crucible and reweighed. The sample was then oven-dried at 105°C for 30 minutes, cooled in a desiccator for 15 minutes, and then reweighed using an analytical balance.^[11]

$$\% \text{ Water content} = \times 100\% \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1 - W_0}$$

Information:

W0 = Weight of empty porcelain cup (g)

W1 = Weight of porcelain cup + sample before heating (g)

W2 = Weight of porcelain cup + sample after heating (g)

Steam distillation

500 g of cinnamon bark was placed in a kettle on a distillation apparatus. Next, 1 L of distilled water was added to the distillation apparatus. The distillation flask was closed and the steam distillation apparatus was assembled. The distillation process was carried out for 3 hours at a temperature of 100-105°C. To obtain the yield of cinnamon bark essential oil, the following formula was used.^[12]

$$\% \text{ rendemen} = \frac{\text{massa minyak atsiri}}{\text{massa sampel awal}} \times 100\%$$

Analysis of essential oils with GC-MS

Analysis using GC-MS aims to determine the majority compound components of the essential oil produced.^[13] The sample was dissolved in n-hexane solvent. A 1 µl sample was injected into the inlet of the GC-MS instrument. The obtained spectra were interpreted based on molecular weight and retention time (Rt). These data identify the type and amount of compounds in cinnamon essential oil.^[13]

Essential oil analysis with FTIR

The essential oil obtained from the distillation was then analyzed using FTIR. FTIR analysis aims to determine the functional groups of a material or the resulting matrix.^[14]

A 2 mg sample and 200 mg KBr were mixed. 2-3 drops of nujjol mull were added to the 2 mg mixture and stirred until homogeneous. Then, the thin plate was molded to form a transparent plate. The thin plate was then inserted into the sample holder and read using an FTIR instrument. The resulting spectra were compared with the FTIR data bank table.^[14]

Manufacture of cinnamon bark essential oil nanoemulsion matrix

The nanoemulsion formulation was made by combining cinnamon bark essential oil, VCO, Tween 80, PEG 400, and distilled water. The oil phase, consisting of cinnamon bark essential oil and VCO, was vortexed for two minutes. Tween 80 was then added to the oil phase and vortexed again for two minutes. Afterward, PEG 400 was added and vortexed for two minutes. The distilled water was added to the mixture of oil, surfactant, and cosurfactant, then vortexed for 30 minutes.^[9]

Table 1: Nanoemulsion Formulation Design.

Ingredients	Formulation				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Cinnamon bark essential oil (g)	0	0,1	0,15	0,2	0,3
VCO (g)	0,3	0,2	0,15	0,1	0
Tween 80 (g)	4	4	4	4	4
PEG 400 (g)	2	2	2	2	2
Distilled water (g)	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,7	3,7
Total (g)	10	10	10	10	10

Test particle size, polydispersity index value, and zeta potential

1 mL nanoemulsion preparation was taken and dissolved in 250 mL of aqua pro injection. The diluted nanoemulsion sample was placed into a cuvette and measured using a Particle Size Analyzer (PSA) for particle size, polydispersity index, and zeta potential. Zeta potential measurements were performed using PSA at 25°C.^[15]

Determination of Nanoemulsion Morphology with Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM)

Morphological analysis of cinnamon bark nanoemulsions was performed using TEM. Samples were dropped onto a copper grid, coated with carbon for 5 seconds with an automatic carbon coater, and dried at room temperature for 24 hours. Once dry, the samples were re-coated with carbon and then placed in a holder for analysis at an accelerating voltage of 120 kV and magnification up to 120,000 times.^[16]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Moisture Content and Steam Distillation of Cinnamon Stick Bark Essential Oil

The test results showed that cinnamon bark powder had a water content of 4.35%. The results obtained were still within the standard quality limit of $\leq 10\%$, indicating that the sample quality was in good condition.^[17] The water content in the material greatly influences the quality of essential oils. If the water content is too high, enzyme activity will increase, and these enzymes can convert the chemical components in the material into other forms.^[18]

Table 2: Yield of Essential Oil.

Repeat	Sample Weight	Essential Oil Weight
1	500 g	3,6208 g
2	500 g	4,7711 g
3	500 g	4,2796 g
Total	1.500 g	12,6715 g
Yield		0,8448±0,0134%

The cinnamon bark essential oil produced from the distillation process is 12.6715 g light yellow. The yield of essential oils obtained was $0.8448 \pm 0.0134\%$. Low yield values can be caused by the size of the cut that is still too large so that it inhibits the release of volatile compounds during distillation. In addition, technical factors such as steam pressure and the quality of distillation equipment also affect the amount of essential oils produced.

GC-MS Analysis of Cinnamon Stick Peel Essential Oil

The composition of essential oils contained in cinnamon bark extract analyzed using GC-MS is presented in Figure 1 and Table 3.

Figure 1: GC-MS Spectra of Cinnamon Bark Essential Oil.

Table 3: Chemical Composition of Cinnamon Bark Essential Oil.

No	Composition	Composition	Time Retention	Area	Area (%)	m/f
1	Camphene		8.266	44128792	18.432	93.00
2	Benzaldehyde (CAS) Phenylmethanal		8.562	13148553	5.492	77.00
3	2-Beta-Pinene		8.806	62642752	26.165	93.00

4	Beta Terpineol		9.830	20142182	8.413	68.00
5	1,8-Cineole		9.880	14209053	5.935	43.00
			9.929	23489395	9.811	43.00
6	3-Cyclohexene-1-methanol-alpha-alpha-4-tr		12.441	8700257	3.634	59.00
			12.692	8293558	3.464	59.00
7	2-Propenal-3-phenyl- (CAS) Cinnamaldehyde		13.683	42137788	17.600	131.00
			13.870	2525010	1.055	131.00

The chemical composition of essential oils from cinnamon bark based on GC-MS analysis showed that the main components identified were 2- β -pinene (18,343%), camphene (17,799%), and *cinnamaldehyde* (17,600%).

The content of *cinnamaldehyde* plays an important role as a key determinant of the biological activity of cinnamon essential oils, particularly as an antibacterial, antifungal, and antioxidant.^[19] The combination of *cinnamaldehyde* with monoterpene compounds (β -pinene, camphene, 1,8-cineole) provides a synergistic effect in enhancing the antibacterial potential of essential oils.^[20]

β -pinene and camphene are known to be monoterpenes that are lipophilic so they are able to penetrate the cell membrane of bacteria, disrupt membrane integrity, and inhibit microbial growth.^[21] Meanwhile, 1,8-cineole is reported to have anti-inflammatory activity and can strengthen the permeability of bacterial lipid membranes, thereby increasing the effectiveness of other phenolic compounds in essential oils.^[22]

The *benzaldehyde content* contributes to its antibacterial properties as it can cause damage to cell membrane proteins.^[23] Meanwhile, minor compounds such as β -terpineol and 3-Cyclohexene-1-methanol derivatives remain relevant, albeit in low levels, as these compounds of the aromatic alcohol group are able to strengthen antibacterial activity.^[23]

Manufacture of Cinnamon Stick Bark Essential Oil Nanoemulsion

The spontaneous emulsification method was chosen in this study because it is a simple, non-high-energy, and effective method for producing nanoemulsions, especially when working with sensitive compounds such as essential oils.^[24] The main advantage of this method is its ability to form nano-sized droplets through a mass transfer and voltage drop mechanism interface, without the need for high pressure or special tools. The use of this method also allows the process to take place at low to medium temperatures, so that the active content in essential oils, such as *cinnamaldehyde*, is not degraded by overheating.^[24]

The emulsification process is carried out in stages by using a vortex mixer, which produces a quick circular vibration to mix the components evenly. The emulsification time was 30 minutes to achieve initial stability of the system and form droplets of more uniform size.^[25] During the process, physicochemical reactions occur such as a decrease in surface tension by surfactants, the formation of a stable interface layer around the oil droplets, as well as the displacement of molecules between phases due to differences in polarity and concentration.^[25]

Based on the formulation stages carried out, the nanoemulsions in this study were made using a low-energy emulsification method through the *Phase Inversion Composition* (PIC) mechanism, which is included in *Transitional Phase Inversion* (TPI). As water is gradually added into the oil phase, the amount of water in the system increases. This addition of water causes the polyoxyethylene (POE) chains in the surfactants to become hydrated. As a result, the balance of hydrophilic and lipophilic properties of surfactants changes. Under certain conditions, the curvature of the surfactant is close to zero and a bi-continuous or lamellar structure is formed. The addition of water further causes a change in curvature to be positive, resulting in phase inversion and the formation of nano-sized emulsion droplets due to changes in system composition.^[26]

The results of physical observation of the nanoemulsion formula after the emulsification process, showed a cloudy yellowish-white appearance, which indicates that the formula is not completely homogeneous. This condition occurs because the size of the droplets is still diverse and many air bubbles are trapped due to strong agitation during emulsification. The bubbles appear to stick to the walls of the tube and will reduce after being left alone. There is no visible separation of the oil and water phases, suggesting that surfactants and cosurfactants have worked quite well in the early stages of nanoemulsion formation.^[27]

Characterization with Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The FTIR spectrum is used to identify the main functional groups in cinnamon bark essential oils and evaluate the interaction between the components that make up the nanoemulsion.

Figure 3: FTIR spectrum: (a) cinnamon bark essential oil, (b) F1 formula nanoemulsion, (c) F2 formula nanoemulsion, (d) F3 formula nanoemulsion, (e) F4 formula nanoemulsion, and (f) F5 formula nanoemulsion.

The FTIR spectrum of essential oils shows that in an area of about 3400 cm^{-1} there is a band with high transmittance, which indicates weak absorption rather than strong absorption. This suggests that the content of the -OH group in cinnamon bark essential oil is relatively small, or that the intensity of vibration is masked by other components that are more dominant. A band with strong absorption was actually seen at 1730 cm^{-1} , which came from the stretching vibration C=O of the aldehyde group, indicating the presence of cinnamaldehyde as the main component. The aromatic C=C stretching vibration was detected at 1600 cm^{-1} , while the band at $2920\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ showed the aliphatic C-H stretching typical of terpene compounds. Meanwhile, the band at 1100 cm^{-1} shows a C-O stretching of the alcohol or ether group.

F1 formula is a control formula that does not contain essential oils, but only consists of VCO, Tween 80, PEG 400, and distilled water. The spectrum showed weak absorption at 3400 cm^{-1} (stretching $-\text{OH}$ of PEG 400) and bands at $2920\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-H aliphatic of VCO). Strong absorption at $1100\text{--}1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates C-O stretching of ether and alcohol groups. There are no typical aromatic C=O or C=C bands of active compounds.

The F2 formula with the addition of 0.1 g of essential oils began to show a new band at 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O aldehyde) and a shift at 1600 cm^{-1} (C=C aromatic). The band widens at 3400 cm^{-1} indicating the formation of a hydrogen bond between the essential oil, surfactant, and cosurfactant components. This indicates the initial integration of the active compound into the nanoemulsion system.

In Formula F3, the proportion of essential oils was increased to 0.15 g and VCO was lowered to 0.15 g. Formula F3 showed an increase in the absorption intensity of $-\text{OH}$ (3400 cm^{-1}) and C=O (1730 cm^{-1}), as well as a small shift in C-O (1100 cm^{-1}), indicating stronger hydrogen bonds and intermolecular interactions. The 1450 cm^{-1} band (bending C-H) is increasingly prominent, indicating an increased contribution of the aliphatic group of the essential oil and surfactant components.

The F4 formula has a higher concentration of essential oils (0.2 g) and only 0.1 g of VCO. The F4 spectrum shows a significantly widened $-\text{OH}$ band (3400 cm^{-1}), indicating an increase in the number of intermolecular hydrogen interactions. The 1730 cm^{-1} (stretching C=O) peak is getting stronger, indicating an increase in synamaldehyde content. The bands of $2920\text{--}2850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (stretching C-H) remained stable, and the 1100 cm^{-1} (stretching C-O) showed an increase in intensity due to the increased number of ether groups from Tween 80 and PEG 400.

F5 formula is the formula with the highest essential oil (0.3 g) and no added VCO. The F5 spectrum shows the strongest peaks for C=O (1730 cm^{-1}) and aromatic C=C (1600 cm^{-1}), as well as significant widening at $-\text{OH}$ (3400 cm^{-1}) due to intense hydrogen interactions. The C-H bending vibrations (1450 cm^{-1}) and C-O (1100 cm^{-1}) stretching are also becoming more pronounced, suggesting that the nanoemulsion system has stabilized the essential oil components without changing the structure of their main functional groups.

Table 4: Comparison of FTIR spectra.

Number of Gelombang (cm ⁻¹)	Gugus Fungsi	Cinnamon Essential Oil	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
3800–3200	O–H (hydroxyl)	3397,34	3701,96	2990,86	3722,77	2961,82	3725,67
	N–H	3399,65	-	-	-	-	-
3200–2700	C–H alifatik	2927,33	2990,86	2990,86	2989,93	2961,82	2957,97
1750–1600	C=O (carbonyl)	1727,33	2342,65	2341,68	2341,68	2340,72	2344,96
1500–1400	C–H alifatik	1447,13	1483,93	1500,86	1460,07	1494,90	1494,90
1300–1000	C–O alcohol	1166,02	1164,09	1164,09	1163,13	1165,06	1160,23
	C–N	1017,49	879,95	879,58	868,97	879,56	870,90
<700	Aromatic C=C double bond	614,35	-	-	-	-	-

The results of the FTIR spectrum analysis showed the presence of an N–H absorption band in cinnamon bark essential oil at a wavenumber of about 3399 cm⁻¹, but this band was not detected in the entire nanoemulsion formula. The loss of the N–H band in the nanoemulsion formula is due to the overlapping between the O–H stretch band (3400–3200 cm⁻¹) of the surfactant Tween 80 and the co-surfactant PEG 400 with the N–H band (about 3399 cm⁻¹) of the essential oil.^[28] Both materials have hydroxyl groups with very high vibrational intensity, so they can mask or weaken N–H signals until they are no longer detectable in the FTIR spectrum. In addition, the emulsification process can lead to the formation of hydrogen bonds between the N–H group of the essential oil and the O–H group of the surfactant, which also results in a shift or loss of peak due to a decrease in vibrational energy.^[29]

In the FTIR spectrum of cinnamon bark essential oils, there is a typical absorption band in an area of about 1600 cm⁻¹ which shows the stretching vibration of the aromatic C=C group. These bands are derived from the main compounds of essential oils such as cinnamaldehyde and eugenol which have an aromatic ring structure.^[30] However, once the essential oil is formulated into a nanoemulsion, this band becomes weak or even invisible due to the interaction of hydrogen and van der Waals force between the essential oil molecules with the surfactant causing a shift in position or a decrease in the intensity of the absorption band, as the electronic environment around the C=C group changes. This does not mean that the C=C group is chemically lost, but is covered by other strong absorption bands such as –OH (3400 cm⁻¹) and C–O (1100 cm⁻¹) derived from PEG 400 and Tween 80.^[30]

The formulas F1 to F5 have the same FTIR spectral pattern, which means that all of its constituents can be detected. While cinnamon bark essential oils contain –OH, C=O aldehyde, C=C aromatic, and N–H groups, some groups such as N–H and C=C aromatics are

not visible in the nanoemulsion formula, instead the –OH and C–O groups of Tween 80, PEG 400, and VCO are more prominent in the formula even though they are not dominant in essential oils.

Based on the results of the FTIR spectrum analysis, it can be concluded that the nanoemulsion formulation process does not change the main chemical structure of cinnamon bark essential oils, but only causes a shift in the absorption band due to physical interactions such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between essential oils with surfactants and cosurfactants. This shows that the main active compounds such as *cinnamaldehyde* remain stable in the nanoemulsion system and without chemical degradation, which signifies the success of the chemical emulsification process and good formulation stability.

Karakterisasi Particle Size Analyzer (PSA)

The results of the Particle Size Analyzer (PSA) analysis showed that the overall formula of cinnamon bark essential oil nanoemulsions resulted in very small particle sizes, ranging from 9.76 to 12.92 nm. The PSA test results from formula 1 to 5 can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Particle size, PDI, and zeta potential of nanoemulsions.

Nanoemulsi	Particle size (nm)	Polydispersity index	Zeta potential (mV)
Formula F1	11,58	0,0528	-13,68
Formula F2	12,76	0,1610	- 15,33
Formula F3	11,18	0,2128	- 11,48
Formula F4	10,41	0,1122	- 9,956
Formula F5	9,786	0,0652	- 11,01

The results obtained indicated that the nanoemulsion formed had a droplet size according to the nanoemulsion criteria, which was in the range of 20–500 nm, and showed a polydispersity index (PI) value that was close to zero. A low PI value (< 0.3) reflects an improved degree of uniformity of globule size in the preparation.^[31] Formula F1 (0.0528) and Formula F5 (0.0652) show a very narrow size distribution (monodisperse), reflecting a homogeneous system. Formula F2 (0.161) and Formula F4 (0.1122) are still in the good category, while Formula F3 has the highest value (0.2128), indicating a slightly wider size distribution, but still within acceptable limits for nanoemulsions. The speed of stirring plays an important role in influencing the value of the polydispersity index in the nanoemulsion. If the stirring is too fast, the particles can collide with each other causing them to increase in size and the

preparation to become cloudy. On the other hand, when stirring is too slow, the resulting preparations tend to be inhomogeneous.^[32]

The F5 formula has the smallest particle size (9,786 nm), which indicates its high potential in providing greater surface area, better light distribution, and more efficient penetration. The size of the nanoemulsion particles affects the speed of release and absorption of the drug. Smaller particles are more easily absorbed by the body, thus being able to accelerate the achievement of the effect.^[32]

The zeta potential value ranges from -9.96mV to -15.33 mV. The F2 formula gives the greatest zeta potential value of -15.33 mV although this value is still below ± 30 mV. This is predicted because the F5 formula nanoemulsion is strongly influenced by the steric stability mechanism provided by non-ionic surfactants (Tween 80) and cosurfactants (PEG-400).^[33]

Overall, F5 formula nanoemulsions excel in terms of particle size and narrow distribution making them the most kinetically stable candidate and functionally efficient. The nanoemulsion of the F1 formula shows very high homogeneity (low PDI). Meanwhile, the F2 formula nanoemulsion shows the best of its electrostatic repellent properties.^[34]

Characterization with Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

The results of the Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) test on cinnamon bark essential oil showed a clear difference at 500 nm and 50 nm magnification. At the 500 nm scale, the particles appear to be distributed fairly evenly despite the tendency to form small aggregates. This is due to the hydrophobic properties of essential oils which are prone to clumping due to the van der Waals force between particles.^[35] Magnified by 50 nm magnification, essential oil particles appear more clearly with a rounded to semi-rounded shape and size in the nanometer range. The particle surface appears relatively smooth and homogeneous, although there are indications of coalescence between adjacent particles.

Figure 4: TEM test results: (a) F1 formula nanoemulsion, (b) F2 formula nanoemulsion, (c) F3 formula nanoemulsion, (d) F4 formula nanoemulsion, and (e) F5 formula nanoemulsion.

The morphology of cinnamon bark essential oil nanoemulsion particles in the F1 formula shows a spherical shape with fairly even distribution, which indicates that the emulsification process is going well. The F2 formula shows spherical particles but their distribution is not uniform and there is an indication of aggregation, thus showing more variable particle sizes. The F3 formula features spherical particles with a larger size than other formulas, but a clear appearance indicates that a nanoemulsion system is still formed.

The F4 formula produces spherical particles with a small size and a larger number of particles, accompanied by a homogeneous distribution. These characteristics indicate that essential oils are successfully dispersed well in the nanoemulsion system. The F5 formula still shows spherical particles but with a more diverse size and tends to undergo light aggregation, although it remains in the nanometer range.

Overall, the TEM results show that the entire formula successfully forms spherical particles at the nanometer scale, with the F4 formula having the best morphology due to its small particle size, even distribution, and more particle count, potentially improving the stability of the nanoemulsion.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussions that have been presented, the conclusions of this study are as follows.

1. Cinnamon bark essential oil contains the compounds Camphene, Benzaldehyde (CAS) Phenylmethanal, 2-Beta-Pinene, Beta Terpineol, 1,8-Cineole, 3-Cyclohexene-1-methanol-alpha-alpha-4-tr, and 2-Propenal-3-phenyl- (CAS) Cinnamaldehyde.
2. The effect of cinnamon bark essential oil and VCO formulations on the physicochemical characteristics of the resulting nanoemulsions showed that the formulations affected the particle size, zeta potential, and morphology of the nanoemulsions formed.
3. Formula F4 was the best formulation with a particle size of 10.41 nm, low PDI, and the best stability based on FTIR, zeta potential, and TEM analysis.

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